

METHODOLOGICAL BASES OF LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF POETRY TRANSLATION

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Annotation

Poetic language, at least in some theorizations, differs from the everyday, ordinary language. In ordinary usage, language is mostly automatic, and words are used in a way that does not attract attention, but in poetry the language is used in such a special way that the reader makes a distinction between poetic language and the daily or usual one.

Key words: *metalingual, neologism, poetic language, disorientation, anthimeria*

INTRODUCTION

Before dealing with this question let us begin with the very notion of language as poetry cannot be imagined outside language. There have been many different definitions for the term. Pei defines language as “a system of communication by sound, operating through the organs of speech and hearing, among members of a given community, and using vocal symbols possessing arbitrary conventional meanings”¹. As Hall puts it, “language is the institution whereby humans communicate

¹ Pei, M. (1966). *How to Learn Languages and What Languages to Learn*. New York: Harper & Row Publishers

and interact with each other by means of habitually used oral-arbitrary systems”². What is common in these definitions is that „language is a means of communication“. However, language is not just a way of communicating daily needs. It also speaks about the cultural loads of centuries, beliefs, traditions and thoughts. To put it in different words, language performs different functions. Jakobson (1981) assumes six basic functions for language: emotive, conative, phatic, metalingual, referential and poetic. Among these functions, poetic function is related to the aesthetic and artistic aspects of language and is mainly used in literature and poetry.

DISSCUSSION AND RESULTS

Although Jacobson does not reduce the domain of poetic function to poetry, he considers it to be the dominant and determining function of verbal art, whereas in all other verbal activities “... it acts as a subsidiary, accessory constituent”. Halliday uses the term „textual function“ and Martinet „aesthetic function“ to refer to this function of language. Literary language and poetry as a part of it use this function to a great extent whereby make the language more beautiful.

In principle, the language of poetry comes into existence when some norms are broken or deviated from. According to Shafii-Kadkani, “poetry is nothing but breaking the norms of ordinary and logical language”³. Shamisa (2004) also believes that there is almost no literary work that does not involve a sort of deviation from ordinary language and assumes that the subject of linguistic deviation should not be neglected because in some cases all of the importance and influence of a literary work depends on it.

Leech (1969) argues that any deviation from expected patterns of linguistic behavior will bring about a reaction of disorientation and surprise. Rules in poetry,

² Hall, R. A. (1968). *An Essay on Language*. New York: Chilton Books.

³ Shafii Kadkani, M. (1989). *Musighie sher. Music of Poetry*. 2nd edition (extended and revised text). Tehran: Agah publications

Leech elaborates, are made to be broken (10-12)⁴. Leech observed that looking back over the span of English literature since Chaucer; we note that certain freedoms of language have been traditionally sanctioned in verse, but not in prose (17-23). Leech remarked:

The obvious function of these freedoms is to compensate the poet for his loss of freedom in submitting himself to the discipline of verse composition; to furnish him with a wider set of choices than are normally available in English and thus to give him a better chance of squeezing his language into a predetermined mould of versification.

Neologism, or the invention of new words, is one of the more obvious ways in which a poet exceeds the normal resources of the language. Leech calls new words “nonce-formations” if they are made for the nonce, i.e., for a single occasion only. The English rule of word formation permits prefixation of “fore-” to a verb, to convey the meaning “beforehand” as in foresee, foreknow, foretell and forewarn. If this rule were completely free in its application, we would use verbs such as foresell (sell in advance) or foreappear (appear in advance) without even noticing their oddity. But the rule is in fact limited to a small group of vocabulary items. For instance, in "The Waste Land" T.S. Eliot augments the group by using the verb “foresuffered” in the line:

And I Tiresias have foresuffered all

This strikes us as a novelty and as a surprising extension of the expressive possibilities of the language. Leech maintains that “Eliot’s “foresuffered” is not just a new word, but the encapsulation of a newly formulated idea; that it is possible to anticipate mystically the suffering of the future just as it is

⁴Leech, Geoffrey. (1969). *A Linguistic Guide to English Poetry*. London & New York: Longman.

possible to foresee, foretell, or have foreknowledge of future events.

Forming new words using affixes is another process used by poets. For examples Eliot invented “*unflowering*.”

*And growing between them, indifference
Being between two lives - **unflowering**, between
The live and the dead nettle ("Little Gidding" III: 4-7)*

Jeffries (1993) contends that poets are sometimes influenced by spoken language in their lexical choices. The influence may be from a number of different sources. It may be, for example, the choice of a poet to use a regionally distinct vocabulary or vocabulary that is clearly colloquial, possibly even slang or taboo. The reasons why poets make such choices are also varied; the desire to escape from a standard language which is seen as oppressive, the wish to use a spoken style for certain characters in poems, and the intention to shock readers by using vocabulary that is not often seen in print⁵. Other poets challenge reader's expectations about lexical selection, for example, by using words assigned to one syntactic class as if they were members of another, for instance the rhetorical figure known as anthimeria. Thus "did" and "didn't" act as nouns in e. cumming's line " he sang his **didn't** he danced **did** " , and "grief " becomes a temporal expression in Dylan Thomas's " a grief ago. ".

Jeffries (1993) argues that poets have not hesitated to use a grammar which reflects everyday usage or the cultural background of the poet (35). Jeffries evidence is that Kofi Anyidoho, in his poem “My Mailman Friend was Here”, uses a grammatical structure typical of a West African pidgin. For example, "I go write you something small again" has a verb phrase form which differs from the standard

⁵ Jeffries, Lesley. (1993). *The Language of Twentieth-Century Poetry*. London: The Macmillan Press Ltd.

English am going to write, and this is followed by a pronoun you which in standard English would be introduced by a preposition "to" as it is an indirect object. Minor sentences, sentences without a finite verb, are one way that poets vary their grammatical structures. Both of the following examples are from "Canticle for Good Friday" by Geoffrey Hill. The first consists of a NP not followed by a verb of any kind,

A clamping cold-figured day

while, the second contains subject and complement but no verb to create a full sentence

He, as yet unsearched, unscratched

The effect of avoiding using main verbs in poetry may be used to render the poem timeless, thus achieving the purpose of not anchoring the action in a particular time span.

Moreover, word order, as mentioned in George M. Landon's article (1968:194-200) is a syntactic violation. He proposes the view that sentences such as (1a) and (2a) below exhibiting an unusual word order may be described as violating certain rules which would have yielded the corresponding, sequentially well-formed sentences (1b) and (2b).

1. a. Our sons their fathers' failing language see (Pope).
b. Our sons see their fathers' failing language.
2. a. By them had slimy paths been trailed and scraped (Owen)
b. Slimy paths had been trailed and scraped by them.

Along the same line of argument, another freedom poets have enjoyed by custom is the arranging of syntactic elements in an irregular order (*hyperbaton*). Jumbled clause structures have been taken so much for granted in verse. The opening two stanzas of Cowper's "The Diverting History of John Gilpin" contain three examples:

John Giloin was a citizen

Of credit and renown,
A train-band captain eke was he
 Of famous London town
 John Gilpin's spouse said to her dear,
 Though ***wedded we have been***
 These twice ten tedious years; ***yet we***
No holiday have seen.

The sections in bold italics each contains the main clause elements subject (s), verbal (v), and object/complement(c), which in prose, as in ordinary speech, would almost certainly occur in the order SVC. Cowper gives us three separate variations of that order: CVS, CSV, and SCV.

Furthermore, poetic language may violate or deviate from the generally observed rules of the language in many ways, i.e., word order, pleonasm, ellipses. Word order includes fronting, postponement and passivization. See (Brook, 1958, Leech, 1969; Roscow, 1981; Traugott, 1972; Dillon, 1975 and Dillon, 1976). These processes characterize the unusualness of syntax in poetry. In fact, most of them could be viewed as a relaxation of the constraints on transformations in Modern English (i.e. licenses), (cf. Dillon, 1975)⁶.

CONCLUSION

Based on what was said, the reasonable conclusion to arrive at may be that a literal method of translation is generally useful in the case of linguistic deviations because exclusion or omission of these poetic devices may have drastic effects on the style of the text. For example, in the case of historical and lexical deviations, the translator should try his/her best to create new words and compounds (just like that of original poems), and also make use of archaic words and combinations accessible in English. However, the translator should be careful so that creating new

⁶ Dr. Khalil Hassan Nofal Head/Department of English and Director Language Centre at Philadelphia University Jordan Syntactic Aspects of Poetry: A Pragmatic Perspective

combinations and using archaism may not mar the unity or naturalness of the translation.

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